

R-CURVES CHARACTERIZATION OF GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of several parameters on R-curves characterization of Glass/Epoxy composites, such as specimen thickness, laminate lay-up and loading mode. DCB mode I tests were carried out statically on both unidirectional and multidirectional specimens. The unidirectional specimens have been also tested under mixed mode loading. Different data reduction methods have been realized on DCB unidirectional tests, and It was revealed that for the specimen having small a/h ratio, the shape of R-curves depends strongly on the data reduction methods. Results obtained in composite resistance to delamination extension showed increasing with crack growth until a stable value, G_{Ip-s} , which seemed independent of initial crack length, but varying with specimen thickness, laminate lay-ups as well as the loading mode. If fibre bridging and fibre breaking were the essential causes of rising R-curves, the relationship between the R-curves and these parameters has to be established. A fractography study is being realized in attempt to associate the fibre bridging and breaking process with the stable crack propagation values G_{Ip-s} .

INTRODUCTION

Delamination due to interlaminar stresses is a dominant failure mode in the laminated composite structures. Therefore, the delamination problem must be well understood before efficient composite structure can be designed. Much attention has been focused on the characterization of delamination behaviour by using one approach of fracture mechanics: fracture toughness in term of the strain energy release rate G . Various specimens have been proposed to determine the critical G values under mode I, Mode II and mode III as well as mixed mode loadings. In these tests, the interlaminar fracture toughness corresponding to the initiation of crack growth was found varying with the loading mode. Moreover, a considerable increase in resistance to delamination extension (R-curve), even for one given loading mode, has been indicated for much composites. If the former can be explained by the different damage zone at the crack tip, which seemed unchanging for a composite system under a given loading condition [1, 2], the latter has been believed a consequence of the fibre bridging [3-8]. Some works have showed that one stable value in the resistance to delamination extension can be attained after certain crack extension. So it is natural to think that the ideal characterization of the delamination resistance must be performed with two values: G_C and G_{p-s} corresponding to the initiation and to the extension of delamination, respectively. However, it seems that the G_{p-s} value depends not only the loading condition, the nature of the composite system, but also on specimen geometry. According to the results for Carbon/Epoxy specimens of three thicknesses presented by Russell and Street [3], the stable

gave the same impression. On contrary, the work of Phillips and Wells [4] showed a decrease in delamination extension resistance as the specimen thickness increased from 15 to 55mm. It is clear that the geometry dependence will make the stable extension resistance value of little practical use unless we can understand it and predict it.

The purpose of this study is so to investigate the composite resistance to delamination extension in Glass/Epoxy composites and to clarify the problems in the characterization of the R-curves. Unidirectional Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens with different thickness and the multidirectional DCB ones were loaded statically under mode I conditions. The unidirectional specimens have been also tested under mixed mode loading by using the Mixed Mode Flexure (MMF) specimens. The effect of the fibre bridging on the R-curves was investigated. The relationship between the stable values $G_{I\text{-}s}$ of the R-curve and specimen geometrical parameters and the loading mode has been discussed. We hope that the experimental results obtained here can help the future modelisation of the fibre bridging.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two quasi-unidirectional E-glass reinforced epoxy resin prepregs were used to prepare specimen panels in this study. Composite 1 (Hexcel 1031/ES67/30%) had 12% fibre woven perpendicularly so as to hold the parallel fibres together, its fibre volume fraction was 55%. Composite 2 (Vicotex M10/38%/1130) had 5% fibre woven and a fibre volume fraction of 52%. These two materials had the same longitudinal flexure modulus, E_{11} , of 36 MPa.

Specimens

Unidirectional DCB specimens with different thickness were prepared from panels of composite 1. Unidirectional MMF specimens and multidirectional DCB specimens were prepared from the panel of 50 plis (2h=20mm) and 16 plis (2h=6mm) respectively of composite 2. The lay-ups of panels was [(0₃/90)_s]_s and [(±θ)₂]_s with θ= 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°. The symmetrical stratification ensured the pure mode I delamination under DCB loading condition. All panels were moulded using a hot press and a Teflon film inserted at mid-thickness during fabrication served as the crack starter. All specimens had a width of about 20mm and a sufficient length for crack propagation.

Test conditions

Tests were conducted at the room temperature with a small displacement rate (from 0.5 to 5 mm/min). The thin specimens were loaded with help of the tabs attached at ends and the thick ones with through pins. The specimens were instrumented by strain gauges and acoustic emission receiver to detect the initiation of delamination. Their responses as well as the load and displacement were recorded during the test served to determine the delamination resistance and to analyse the delamination mechanisms

DATA-REDUCTION METHODS

The determination of composite toughness of delamination in term of the strain energy release rate was performed by applying the compliance method based on the Irwin-Kies equation:

$$G_c = \frac{P_c^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (1)$$

where P_c is the critical load, B the width, C the compliance defined by the displacement (δ) over the load (P) and a the crack length.

This method requires an expression relating specimen compliance to crack length, which can be obtained analytically or experimentally. A lot of analytical models have been developed for different delamination specimens, however, it is difficult for an analytical model to take account of all of phenomena, such as the presence of the crack tip, shear, material anisotropy as well as the influence of test apparatus. Until present, the application of these models to composite specimens does not give a total satisfaction. In fact, the study of delamination extension requires to know the crack length during crack propagation, but the measurement of the crack length

would be perturbed by the fibre bridging. So a good compliance expression could give an effective crack length and in turn a good result of G . Hence, in this study we prefer an experimental approach that translates better the reality.

In general, starting from an analytical model, the experimental compliance expression was proposed with various constants. These constants must be determined empirically by interpolating the specimen compliance measurements relating to different initial crack length.

In the case of DCB specimens, the compliance calibration introduced by Berry can be written as [2, 8]:

$$C = \frac{a^n}{m} \quad (2)$$

Applying the equation (1), the energy G_{Ic} corresponding to delamination initiation can be calculated by:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{n P_c \delta_c}{2 B a} \quad (3)$$

Where P_c and δ_c must be the load and displacement at the initiation of delamination. After the initiation, the effective crack length (a -eff) as well as the corresponding energy values (G_{Ip}) can be obtained by following formulas:

$$a\text{-eff} = \sqrt[n]{\frac{m \delta_e}{P_e}}, \quad G_{Ip} = \frac{n P_e \delta_e}{2 B a\text{-eff}} \quad (4)$$

Note that P_e and δ_e represent the load and corresponding displacement during delamination extension.

Another compliance approach for DCB specimen has been proposed by Williams et al. [9-11]

$$C = N \frac{8(a+\chi h)^3}{B h^3 E_{II}} \quad (5)$$

where N and χ are two correction factors. In our study, this model was rewritten as:

$$C = \alpha(a+\beta)^3 \quad (6)$$

α and β can be found empirically. By the same way, the energy values at the delamination initiation and during the delamination extension as well as the effective crack length may thus be obtained by

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{3\alpha P_c \delta_c}{2B(a+\beta)} \quad (7)$$

$$a\text{-eff} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\delta_e}{P_e} \frac{1}{\alpha} - \beta}, \quad G_{Ip} = \frac{3\alpha P_e \delta_e}{2B(a\text{-eff}+\beta)} \quad (8)$$

In the case of MMF specimens, the experimental compliance model employed is expressed as [12]

$$C = q + k a^3 \quad (9)$$

The initiation values G_{Ic} , extension values G_{Ip} and a -eff can be determined by

$$G_{(I+II)c} = 3k a^2 \frac{P_c^2}{2B} \quad (10)$$

$$a\text{-eff} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\delta_e}{k P_e} - \frac{q}{k}}, \quad G_{(I+II)p} = 3k (a\text{-eff})^2 \frac{P_e^2}{2B} \quad (11)$$

This model has been applied for different mixed mode ratio with success, so we have also tried to apply it to DCB mode I case .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Comparison of data-reduction methods

In order to investigate the specimen thickness effect on the material resistance to the delamination extension, DCB tests were performed on the unidirectional composite 1 of four thickness :2h=6.3, 12.7, 15.4 and 20.6mm. For each thickness, compliances were measured on twelve specimens with different initial crack length. These results were interpreted with three experimental compliance calibrations mentioned above. Table 1 presents the constants n of Berry's compliance calibration (Eq.4). It is showed that n decreases with the specimen thickness and when 2h=20.6mm, it was about 2 instead of 3 predicted by the simple beam theory .

Table 1 Constant n of Berry's compliance calibration

2h (mm)	6.3	12.7	15.4	20.6
n	2.6407	2.4012	2.0724	1.9542

Fig.1 Comparison of data-reduction methods (Unidirectional DCB specimens of composite 1)

Moreover, R-curves obtained by Berry' method (Eq.4) showed an interesting tendency. For the specimens with high a/h ratio, the resistance to delamination propagation increased rapidly in a first ten millimetre and then attained a quasi-stable value (Fig.1-A). In the case of small a/h ratio, the propagation resistance increased at beginning, but it dropped down and seemed to tend to a stable value (Fig.1-B). If Berry's method gave a correct R-curve, this drop in propagation resistance would be explicable. Note that the crack extension rate was controlled in the range of 0.1 and 0.5 mm/s, it would not be the cause of this resistance drop. It seems difficult to find a reasonable explanation for this phenomenon. In attention of comparison, we have tried Williams's model but only by interpolating the measured compliances to determine two constants α and β in the equation 6. The equations 9-11 have been also applied in mode I case. The results so obtained are also showed in the figure 1. It is seen that three methods, in the case of high a/h ratio, give an excellent agreement (Fig.1-A). However, when the a/h is small, the difference between these methods becomes considerable (Fig. 1-B). R-curve obtained by the equations 11 appears more reasonable while Williams's method gave a R-curve located between those obtained by equations 4 and 8.

Interlaminar fracture resistance - R-curve

Table 2 G_{IC} values for composite 1

2h (mm)	6.3	12.7	15.4	20.6
G_{IC} (N/m)	384.1	375.6	409.6	373.9
E.T.	44.7	85.5	75.3	82.2

In this study, unidirectional mode I DCB specimens of composite 1 were tested to investigate the effects of several specimen geometry on the delamination resistance, in particular, that of the initial crack length and the specimen thickness. Four specimen thickness varying from 6.3 to 20.6mm have been used. For each thickness, four or five specimens with different initial crack length have been loaded up to the crack propagation. The G_{IC} and G_{IP} values, corresponding respectively to the initiation and propagation plateau of delamination, were determined by using equations 10 and 11. Table 2 presents the G_{IC} values. No significant variation in G_{IC} value with initial crack length nor with specimen thickness was revealed.

R-curves in mode I of composite 1 are showed in figure 2 as plots of G_{IP} versus the corresponding effective crack length, a-eff, and several interesting points were indicated. First, the delamination extension resistance increased rapidly from an initiation value as the crack growth, and after about ten millimetre in crack propagation (whatever is specimen thickness!), it attains a plateau, characterized by a cloud of points. This increase in G_{IP} was considered as a result of fibre bridging zone created behind the crack tip[3-7], where fibre debondings and fibre breaking would dissipate more energy. As soon as the fibre bridging zone was saturated, that is to say, the fibre bridges were broken at the same rate as they are created, a stable value G_{IP-s} in crack propagation was attained. It seems that crack extension Δa corresponding to reach of G_{IP-s} value is independent of the specimen thickness. Secondly, for a given specimen thickness, R-curves seemed in general, dependent only of increment of crack growth but not initial crack length (surely with some exception). But the stable propagation values appeared varying with specimen thickness. By calculating roughly an average of G_{IP} values, a light increase with thickness can be observed (to see Table 3). Finally, during tests, crack grew globally in a stable and continuous manner with sometimes a small local unstable crack propagation.

Table 3 G_{IP-s} values for composite 1

2h (mm)	6.3	12.7	15.4	20.6
G_{IP-s} (N/m)	750~1350	900~1170*	900~1250	1050~1450
Average (N/m)	1000	1035	1075	1250

* do not take account of two R-curves with initial crack length of 80 and 100 mm.

Figure 2. crack propagation resistance G_{Ip} versus crack length a_{-eff}
Unidirectional composite 1 under DCB mode I loading

Multidirectional DCB tests were carried out on composite 2. The results obtained are presented in the table 4. Herein, R-curves were obtained by using Berry's compliance calibration. There would be no important effect of data reduction methods on R-curves because of thin specimens. A light variation in G_{Ic} values could be explained by the presence of coupling terms k_y and k_{xy} , which could cause different damage zone at the crack tip[8]. The similar raise in G_{Ip} with crack growth has been observed for all lay-ups, and stable propagation values G_{Ip-s} for each lay-up were evaluated. For lay-ups of $[(\pm\theta_2)s]_s$, stress state and damage zone at crack tip would be different as θ varied, it would not be surprising to obtain a small difference in G_{Ip-s} values. However, crack growth between $0^\circ/0^\circ$ gave a G_{Ip-s} value much more lower. Since all lay-ups had the same nesting of plis, this difference in G_{Ip-s} value could be explained by more side cracks in $[(\pm\theta_2)s]_s$ lay-ups than orthotropic one for forming more fibre bridging.

Table 4. G_{Ic} and G_{Ip-s} values for multidirectional composite 2

Lay-ups	$[(0_3/90)s]_s$	$[(\pm\theta_2)s]_s$	$[(\pm\theta_2)s]_s$	$[(\pm\theta_2)s]_s$	$[(\pm\theta_2)s]_s$
$G_{Ic}(N/m)$	167.830.2	189.943.5	211.833.5	193.88.4	179.235.3
$G_{Ip-s}(N/m)$	667	1210	1152	1131	1160

Mixed mode flexure tests were conducted on 20 mm thick composite 2. Data reduction was realized using equations 9-11. The results obtained are demonstrated in figure 3. Herein, both $G_{(I+II)c}$ and $G_{(I+II)p-s}$ are more important than those in pure mode I. This dependence of loading mode was also observed in Mixed mede bending tests [12].

Figure. 3 Crack propagation resistance G_{Ip} versus crack length $a-eff$ Unidirectional composite 2 under MMF mixed mode loading

CONCLUSIONS

- 1- The shape of R-curves depends on data reduction methods especially for the specimens having small a/h ratio.
- 2- For glass/epoxy composite, delamination resistance increased as crack grew. No significant effects of specimen geometry were investigated on initiation values nor on crack increment Δa at which a stable propagation value was reached. For a given specimen thickness, R-curves in general, depend only on increment of crack growth but not on initial crack length. However, the stable propagation values appeared increasing lightly with specimen thickness.
- 3- If fibre bridging was essential cause of increase composite resistance to delamination propagation, it would be influenced by specimens thickness, lay-ups of laminate and loading mode as well.

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